

Synthesis, characterization and antimicrobial study of *N*-glucosylated 1,3-benzodiazepine-4,7-dione

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Abstract : An efficient synthesis of 2-tetra-*O*-acetyl- β -D-glucopyranosylimino-1,3-di-*H*/aryl/alkyl-[1,2-*e*][1,3]benzodiazepine-4,7-dione by condensation of *N,N'*-di-*H*/aryl/alkyl phthalamide and *N*-tetra-*O*-acetyl- β -D-glucopyranosyl isocyanodichloride in refluxing chloroform has been worked out. The final compounds were characterized on the basis of certain chemical transformations, their IR, ^1H NMR, ^{13}C NMR and mass spectral data. Biological screening of these compounds was carried out against different bacterial strains. They showed moderate activity against pathogenic bacteria. Some of the final compounds were further deacetylated to produce corresponding glucosyl analogues.

Keywords : Phthalamide, isocyanodichloride, 1,3-benzodiazepine-4,7-dione, benzofused-diazepinedione.

Introduction

Carbohydrate derivatives can be used for the synthesis of drugs as these are structurally important components of numerous biologically active natural products. Moreover such type of drugs shows low toxicity and immunogenicity. Thus the interest in the preparation of carbohydrate based drugs is very high.

Benzodiazepines are heterocyclic compounds constituting an important class of biologically active compounds. Owing to this, synthesis of benzodiazepines has been receiving much attention in the field of medicinal and pharmaceutical chemistry. The benzodiazepine nucleus is a pharmacophoric scaffold and possesses a wide range of biological applications¹. Many of them are widely used as anticonvulsant, antianxiety, sedative, antidepressive, hypnotic and neuroleptic agents²⁻⁵. Some heterocycles containing benzodiazepine moiety were reported to possess anti-inflammatory⁶, antiviral⁷, anti-HIV-1⁸, antimicrobial⁹ and antitumor¹⁰ activities. Besides their biological importance, the derivatives of 1,5-benzodiazepines are also commercially used as dyes for acrylic fibres¹¹.

Glycosylation allows water-insoluble and unstable organic compounds to be converted into the corresponding water-soluble and stable compounds, which could prob-

ably improve their bioavailability and pharmacological properties. Presence of glucosyl moiety may result in increase bio adaptability of compound.

Based on literature survey, there is not a single report available to deal with the synthesis of carbohydrate containing benzodiazepinedione and it has been revealed that not much work has been reported on synthesis of 1,3-benzodiazepine-4,7-dione^{12,13}. Owing to such considerations, the synthesis of *N*-glucosylated 1,3-benzodiazepine-4,7-diones have been envisaged.

Results and discussion

Earlier it has been shown that aryl/alkyl isocyanodichlorides have enough potential as a reagent in the synthesis of five and six membered heterocyclic compounds which involves [3+2] and [4+2] cyclo-condensation reaction respectively. Five membered compounds like 1,3-thioxolidines¹⁴, 1,3,4-oxadiazoles¹⁵, 1,2,4-triazoles¹⁶ were synthesized employing these reagents. Similarly, six membered compounds like 1,3,5-triazines^{17,18}, 1,3,5-dithiazines¹⁹ and benzopyrimidines^{15,20} have also been prepared involving the use of these reagents. The use of nucleophilic displacement reactions of *N*-aryl/alkyl isocyanodichlorides have been made in all these cyclo-condensation reactions.

The original intention of our work is to employ *N*-glucosylated isocyanodichloride for the synthesis of seven membered compounds which involves [5+2] cyclo-condensation reaction. Successfully, we have made an use of *N*-glucosylated isocyanodichloride (**4**) in the synthesis of benzodiazepine-4,7-dione (**8**). Compound **4** was synthesized by passing excess chlorine gas into the solution of *N*-glucosylated isothiocyanate in ice cold condition as described in the Experimental section and shown in Scheme 1²¹.

N,N-Di-*H*/aryl/alkyl phthalamide (**7**) was used as starting point for the benzodiazepine nucleus and *N*-tetra-*O*-acetyl-β-D-glucopyranosyl isocyanodichloride (**4**) was used as a reagent for substitution on 2nd position of benzodiaz-

epine nucleus. *N*-Glucosylated 1,3-benzodiazepine-4,7-diones **8(a-h)** were synthesized by refluxing **7(a-h)** with **4** for 4 h in chloroform medium as outlined in Scheme 2. Probable reaction mechanism for the formation of target compounds **8(a-h)** is presented in Fig. 1.

The structures of the target compounds **8(a-h)** and **9(c-e)** were confirmed on the basis of IR, ¹H NMR, ¹³C NMR, and mass spectrometric analysis. The intermediate **4** gave negative lead plumbite test which indicates absence of sulphur. The synthesized compounds **8(a-h)** were charred when treated with concentrated H₂SO₄ indicating the presence of glucosyl moiety. The inductive effect of ester has shifted typical C=O stretching frequency (1710 cm⁻¹) to a higher frequency (1740 cm⁻¹) and absence of

Scheme 1. Synthesis of *N*-tetra-*O*-acetyl-β-D-glucopyranosyl isocyanodichloride (**4**).

Scheme 2. Synthetic route for compounds **8(a-h)** and **9(c,e,g)**.

Fig. 1. Proposed reaction mechanism for the formation of compound **8**.

the band for stretching frequency of the hydroxyl group in IR spectra confirms the formation of acetylated glucosides. The ^1H NMR spectra of **8** showed a characteristic triplet for anomeric proton (H_1) of glucose ring within δ 5.0–5.5 ppm region. Coupling constant (J) within the range 9.0–9.6 Hz indicates glucosyl moiety to be β anomer. Other glucosyl aliphatic protons resonated as multiplet within δ 3.8–5.3 ppm region. The structures of compounds **8(a-h)** were confirmed further by electro spray (ES)-mass spectra showing either a molecular or pseudo-molecular (MH^+) ion peak.

The target compounds **8(c-e)** were deacetylated to give 2- β -D-glucopyranosylimino-1,3-di-(aryl)-[1,2-*e*][1,3]-benzodiazepine-4,7-diones **9(c,e,g)** as described in the Experimental section. IR spectra showed absorption bands at 1742 cm^{-1} for acetyl groups in **8(c,e,g)** which were disappeared in the deacetylated products **9(c,e,g)**. Disappearance of absorption bands at 1742 cm^{-1} for acetyl groups and appearance of absorption bands at 3352 cm^{-1} for hydroxyl groups confirmed the formation of deacetylated glucosides. Results of the present study demonstrate that a new class of different benzodiazepines synthesized from *N,N'*-di-*H*/aryl/alkyl phthalamide (**7**) and evaluated for antibacterial activity. Amongst the tested compounds, **8d** and **8g** were found to be moderately active against *E. coli* and *B. subtilis* respectively.

Conclusion

We have developed eco-friendly, short, simple, and highly reliable route for the synthesis of *N*-glucosy-

lated benzodiazepinediones. This strategy can be successfully applied to prepare a wide range of *N*-glucosylated benzodiazepinedione derivatives for biological evaluation as the benzodiazepinedione core has been widely used for the preparation of biologically active molecules and thus holds great promise towards good active leads in medicinal chemistry. Chloroform and benzene are the solvents of choice for the synthesis of target compounds **8(a-h)** as it is sensitive to protic solvents like ethanol, water, etc.

Experimental

All melting points were uncorrected and obtained in capillary using paraffin bath. FT-IR spectra were recorded using KBr disk on Perkin-Elmer FT-IR KBr spectrophotometer recorded as thin films on KBr pellets with ν_{max} in inverse centimeter. ^1H and ^{13}C NMR spectra were taken on Bruker Avance II 400 NMR spectrometer using $\text{DMSO-}d_6$ and CDCl_3 as solvent and tetramethylsilane (TMS) as internal standard and chemical shifts being reported in parts per million (δ) relative to TMS. The mass spectra were obtained using electron impact (EI) at an ionizing potential of 70 eV. Optical rotations were measured by Equip-Tronics Digital Polarimeter EQ-801. Purity of the compounds was checked on precoated TLC plate using UV light and iodine vapours as a visualizing agent.

Preparation of N-tetra-O-acetyl- β -D-glucopyranosyl isocyanodichloride (4) :

N-Tetra-*O*-acetyl- β -D-glucopyranosyl isocyanodichloride (**4**) was synthesized by dissolving tetra-*O*-acetyl-

β -D-glucopyranosyl isothiocyanate (**3**) (12.8 mmol) in 20 mL chloroform. The chlorine gas generated (from 2.5 g KMnO_4 and 17.5 mL concentrated hydrochloric acid) was passed through it, maintaining temperature 0–5 °C. After complete addition of chlorine gas, yellow reaction mixture was subjected to vacuum distillation. When the sticky mass obtained, it was triturated with petroleum ether to give a creamy solid. It was dissolved in hot benzene and finally petroleum ether was added to cold benzene solution to precipitate out **4** as white solid. (Yield : 5 g, 91%); m.p. 122–123 °C; Molecular formula : $\text{C}_{15}\text{H}_{19}\text{Cl}_2\text{NO}_9$. Characterization was done on the basis of ^1H NMR, IR and mass spectral analysis. Elemental analysis : Calculated : N, 3.27%; Observed : N, 3.10%; IR ν_{max} cm^{-1} : 1654 (C=N), 1742 (O=C-O), 1037 (C-O); ^1H NMR (CDCl_3) δ ppm : 5.32–5.27 (1H, t, J 9.5 Hz, H_1), 5.21–3.81 (6H, m, glucosyl protons), 2.12–2.01 (12H, m, acetyl protons); Mass spectral analysis : m/z M^+ ($\text{Cl}^{35,35}$) 427.

General method for the synthesis of 2-tetra-O-acetyl- β -D-glucopyranosylimino-1,3-di-H/aryl/alkyl-[1,2-e]-[1,3]benzodiazepine-4,7-dione (8a-h) :

2-Tetra-O-acetyl- β -D-glucopyranosylimino-1,3-di-H/aryl/alkyl-[1,2-e][1,3]benzodiazepine-4,7-dione (**8**) was synthesized by adding *N*-tetra-O-acetyl- β -D-glucopyranosylisocyanodichloride (**4**) (1.0 mmol) to the stirred solution of *N,N'*-di-H/aryl/alkyl phthalamide (**7**) (1.0 mmol) in chloroform medium. Reaction mass was allowed to reflux for 4 h during which evolution of hydrogen chloride gas was observed. Progress of the reaction was monitored with TLC. After completion of the reaction, the solvent was evaporated under reduced pressure. Crude product thus obtained was recrystallized from 95% ethanol to give **8(a-h)** as creamy powder.

2-Tetra-O-acetyl- β -D-glucopyranosylimino-1,3-dinaphthyl-[1,2-e][1,3]benzodiazepine-4,7-dione (8a) : Molecular formula : $\text{C}_{43}\text{H}_{37}\text{O}_{13}\text{N}_3$; yield : 0.72 g, 94%, m.p. 106 °C; $[\alpha]_{\text{D}}^{25} = +22.5$; IR ν_{max} cm^{-1} : 1594 (C=N), 1375 (C-N), 1742 (O=C-O); ^1H NMR ($\text{DMSO}-d_6$) δ ppm : 8.21–7.49 (18H, m, Ar-H), 5.41–5.38 (1H, d, J 9.52 Hz, H_1), 5.21–3.80 (6H, m, glucosyl protons), 2.18–1.95 (12H, m, acetyl protons); ^{13}C NMR (CDCl_3) δ ppm : 170.7, 170.2, 169.7, 169.4, 168.8, 167.8, 134.5, 134.4, 132.0, 130.3, 130.0, 128.6, 128.2, 127.1, 127.0,

126.6, 125.4, 123.9, 122.4, 76.8, 69.8, 69.2, 67.8, 61.4, 20.9, 20.7, 20.6, 20.5; Mass analysis : Molecular ion peak (M^+) m/z : 771; related observed peaks 109, 169, 211, 271; R_f : 0.54 (Mobile phase : 30% ethyl acetate-petroleum ether).

2-Tetra-O-acetyl- β -D-glucopyranosylimino-1,3-di-(p-tolyl)-[1,2-e][1,3]benzodiazepine-4,7-dione (8b) : Molecular formula : $\text{C}_{37}\text{H}_{37}\text{O}_{11}\text{N}_3$; yield : 0.5 g, 72%, m.p. 189 °C; $[\alpha]_{\text{D}}^{25} = +15$; IR ν_{max} cm^{-1} : 1560 (C=N), 1020 (C-N), 1743 (O=C-O); ^1H NMR (CDCl_3) δ ppm : 7.89–7.18 (12H, m, Ar-H), 5.25–5.20 (1H, t, J 9.48 Hz, H_1), 5.11–3.60 (6H, m, glucosyl protons), 2.33 (6H, s, $-\text{CH}_3$), 2.03–1.94 (12H, m, acetyl protons); ^{13}C NMR (CDCl_3) δ ppm : 170.6, 170.2, 169.7, 169.4, 168.8, 167.4, 138.2, 134.3, 131.8, 129.8, 129.0, 126.5, 123.7, 89.0, 76.8, 69.8, 69.2, 67.9, 61.4, 21.2, 20.9, 20.7, 20.6, 20.5; Mass analysis : Molecular ion peak (M^+) m/z : 699; related observed peaks 169 and 109; R_f : 0.53 (Mobile phase : 30% ethyl acetate-petroleum ether).

2-Tetra-O-acetyl- β -D-glucopyranosylimino-1,3-di-(o-anisyl)-[1,2-e][1,3]benzodiazepine-4,7-dione (8c) : Molecular formula : $\text{C}_{37}\text{H}_{37}\text{O}_{13}\text{N}_3$; yield : 0.72 g, 98%, m.p. 140 °C; $[\alpha]_{\text{D}}^{25} = +5$; IR ν_{max} cm^{-1} : 1597 (C=N), 1383 (C-N), 1742 (O=C-O), 2968 and 2925 ($-\text{CH}_3$), 1239 (C-O); ^1H NMR ($\text{DMSO}-d_6$) δ ppm : 7.96–7.04 (12H, m, Ar-H), 5.32–5.27 (1H, t, J 9.48 Hz, H_1), 4.27–3.81 (6H, m, glucosyl protons), 3.80 (6H, s, methoxy protons), 2.11–2.02 (12H, m, acetyl protons); Mass analysis : Molecular ion peak (M^+) m/z : 731; observed peak ($\text{M}+1$)⁺ at 732; R_f : 0.62 (Mobile phase : 30% ethyl acetate-petroleum ether).

2-Tetra-O-acetyl- β -D-glucopyranosylimino-1,3-di-(hydro)-[1,2-e][1,3]benzodiazepine-4,7-dione (8d) : Molecular formula : $\text{C}_{23}\text{H}_{25}\text{O}_{11}\text{N}_3$; yield : 0.47 g, 92%, m.p. 108 °C; $[\alpha]_{\text{D}}^{25} = +20$; IR ν_{max} cm^{-1} : 1654 (C=N), 1385 (C-N), 1742 (O=C-O), 3461 (N-H); ^1H NMR ($\text{DMSO}-d_6$) δ ppm : 7.79–7.24 (4H, m, Ar-H), 5.44–5.40 (1H, t, J 9.60 Hz, H_1), 5.28–3.97 (6H, m, glucosyl protons), 2.05–1.91 (12H, m, acetyl protons); Mass analysis : Molecular ion peak (M^+) m/z : 519; observed peak ($\text{M}+1$)⁺ at 520.

2-Tetra-O-acetyl- β -D-glucopyranosylimino-1,3-di-(phenyl)-[1,2-e][1,3]benzodiazepine-4,7 dione (8e) : Molecular formula : $\text{C}_{35}\text{H}_{33}\text{O}_{11}\text{N}_3$; yield : 0.46 g, 69%, m.p.

110 °C; $[\alpha]_D^{25} = +45$; IR ν_{\max} cm^{-1} : 1595 (C=N), 1383 (C-N), 1741.9 (O=C-O); Mass analysis : Molecular ion peak (M^+) m/z : 671; related observed peaks 109, 169, 211, 271, 331; R_f : 0.40 (Mobile phase : 30% ethyl acetate-petroleum ether).

*2-Tetra-O-acetyl- β -D-glucopyranosylimino-1,3-di-(tert-butyl)-[1,2-*e*][1,3]benzodiazepine-4,7-dione (8f)* : Molecular formula $C_{31}H_{41}O_{11}N_3$; yield : 0.43, 68%, m.p. 150 °C; $[\alpha]_D^{25} = +20$; IR ν_{\max} cm^{-1} : 1654 (C=N), 1381 (C-N), 1742 (O=C-O), 2967 and 2924 (-CH₃); Mass analysis : Molecular ion peak (M^+) m/z : 631; related observed peaks 211, 271, 331.

*2-Tetra-O-acetyl- β -D-glucopyranosylimino-1,3-di-(o-tolyl)-[1,2-*e*][1,3]benzodiazepine-4,7-dione (8g)* : Molecular formula : $C_{37}H_{37}O_{11}N_3$; yield : 0.69 g, 99%, m.p. 165 °C; $[\alpha]_D^{25} = +25$; IR ν_{\max} cm^{-1} : 1607 (C=N), 1379 (C-N), 1745 (O=C-O), 2922 (-CH₃); Mass analysis : Molecular ion peak (M^+) m/z : 699; observed peak ($M+1$)⁺ at 700 (base peak); R_f : 0.55 (Mobile phase : 30% ethyl acetate-petroleum ether).

*2-Tetra-O-acetyl- β -D-glucopyranosylimino-1,3-di-(o-chlorophenyl)-[1,2-*e*][1,3]benzodiazepine-4,7-dione (8h)* : Molecular formula : $C_{35}H_{31}O_{11}N_3Cl_2$; yield : 0.73 g, 99%, m.p. 104 °C; $[\alpha]_D^{25} = +27.5$; IR ν_{\max} cm^{-1} : 1690 (C=N), 1377 (C-N), 1743 (O=C-O), 943 (*o*-disubstituted benzene ring); Mass analysis : Molecular ion peak (M^+) m/z : 740; observed peak ($M+1$)⁺ at 741; R_f : 0.50 (Mobile phase : 30% ethyl acetate-petroleum ether).

*Synthesis of 2- β -D-glucopyranosylimino-1,3-di-H/aryl/alkyl-[1,2-*e*][1,3]benzodiazepine-4,7-dione (9c,e,g)* :

2- β -D-Glucopyranosylimino-1,3-di-H/aryl/alkyl-[1,2-*e*][1,3]benzodiazepine-4,7-dione (**9**) was obtained by stirring **8** (0.5 mmol) in 10 ml methanolic ammonia (2 : 3) for 24 h in ice cold condition. A sticky reaction mass was obtained after evaporation which was kept in desiccator to yield a solid crude product. It was recrystallized from methanol.

*2- β -D-Glucopyranosylimino-1,3-di-(o-anisyl)-[1,2-*e*][1,3]benzodiazepine-4,7-dione (9c)* : Molecular formula : $C_{29}H_{29}O_9N_3$; yield : 0.18 g, 64%, m.p. 110 °C; IR ν_{\max} cm^{-1} : 3432 (b) (-OH), 1626 (C=N), 1372 (C-N), 2924 (-CH₃), 1019 (C-O); ¹H NMR (DMSO-*d*₆) δ ppm : 8.20–7.10 (14H, m, Ar-H), 5.80–5.65 (1H, m, H₁), 5.05–4.01 (6H, m, glucosyl protons), 3.98–3.68 (6H, s, methoxy

protons), 3.66 (4H, bs, hydroxyl protons); R_f : 0.30 (Mobile phase : 50% ethyl acetate-petroleum ether).

*2- β -D-Glucopyranosylimino-1,3-di-(o-tolyl)-[1,2-*e*][1,3]benzodiazepine-4,7-dione (9g)* : Molecular formula : $C_{29}H_{29}O_7N_3$; yield : 0.20 g, 75%, m.p. 112 °C; IR ν_{\max} cm^{-1} : 3352 (b) (-OH), 1663 (C=N), 1399 (C-N), 2921 (-CH₃); ¹H NMR (DMSO-*d*₆) δ ppm : 8.26–8.23 (2H, dd, *J* 9.40, 3.48 Hz, Ar-H), 7.96–7.94 (2H, dd, *J* 8.44, 3.00 Hz, benzofused *ortho* Ar-H), 7.89–7.87 (2H, dd, *J* 8.64, 3.00 Hz, benzofused *meta* Ar-H), 7.55–7.52 (2H, dd, *J* 9.0, 3.28 Hz, Ar-H), 7.48–7.43 (4H, m, Ar-H), 5.80–5.78 (1H, d, H₁), 5.03–4.12 (6H, glucosyl protons), 3.92–3.60 (4H, bs, hydroxyl proton), 1.84 (6H, s, CH₃); R_f : 0.28 (Mobile phase : 50% ethyl acetate-petroleum ether).

*2- β -D-Glucopyranosylimino-1,3-di-(phenyl)-[1,2-*e*][1,3]benzodiazepine-4,7-dione (9e)* : Molecular formula : $C_{27}H_{25}O_7N_3$; yield : 0.18 g, 72%, m.p. 140 °C; IR ν_{\max} cm^{-1} : 3350 (b) (-OH), 1605 (C=N), 1388 (C-N), 1078 (C-O); R_f : 0.34 (Mobile phase : 50% ethyl acetate-petroleum ether).

Procedure for antimicrobial screening :

Media used (Nutrient broth) : Peptone - 10 g, NaCl - 10 g and yeast extract 5 g, Agar 20 g in 1000 ml of distilled water. Initially, the stock cultures of bacteria were revived by inoculating in broth media and grown at 37 °C for 18 h. The agar plates of the above media were prepared and wells were made in the plate. Each plate was inoculated with 18 h old cultures (100 μ L, 10⁴ cfu) and spread evenly on the plate. After 20 min, the wells were filled with different concentrations of samples. The control wells were filled with Gentamycin. All the plates were incubated at 37 °C for 24 h and the diameter of inhibition zones were noted in mm.

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